

CONDITIONS CREATED FOR FOREIGN INVESTORS IN UZBEKISTAN

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Our country has a great opportunity and potential to attract foreign investors. Our door is open to all foreign investors who want to invest in our country with underground and surface resources. The most gratifying thing is that peace reigns in Uzbekistan, which is the first opportunity for investors. Also, as a result of the reforms implemented in our country, a number of rights and benefits for investors are being expanded. Uzbekistan Republic of "Investments and Law on investment activities¹ According to Article 34, the concessions and preferences used for state support of investments and investment activities may include:

- Transfer of state-owned objects or property rights to them to an investor at a preferential or zero purchase price;
- Providing tax and payment benefits;
- Subsidizing interest rates on loans the investor takes to implement the investment project.

Privileges and preferences to the following looking given:

- Investment volume;
- The conditions of the place where the investment project will be implemented;
- Expected socio-economic effect and creation of new jobs;
- To areas and sectors of investment project implementation.

According to the list established by attracting foreign direct investments and approved by legislation, the enterprises specializing in the production of products (providing services) in the economic sectors are provided with special features of special tax benefits in accordance with the procedure established by the Tax Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Uzbekistan Republic of Customs to the Codex according to: Customs exemption from duty in the style of tariff privileges to the following relatively is given², including:

- property brought into the customs territory for their production needs by enterprises with participation of foreign investments in the authorized capital

¹Uzbekistan Law of the Republic "On Investments and Investment Activities".

²Customs Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan

(authorized capital) for two years from the time of their state registration, with a share of foreign investments of at least thirty-three percent;

- property imported into the customs territory for the personal needs of foreign investors, citizens of foreign countries staying in the Republic of Uzbekistan and stateless persons permanently living outside the Republic of Uzbekistan in accordance with labor contracts concluded with foreign investors;

- technological equipment, as well as components and spare parts, which are imported into the customs territory according to the list approved in accordance with the law, if they are provided for in the terms of the contract (agreement, agreement) of their delivery.

If the imported technological equipment is sold for export or given free of charge within three years from the moment of importation, the validity of this privilege will be canceled and the obligation to pay customs duties will be restored;

- in the case of changes in the tax legislation within 10 years from the date of state registration of enterprises with participation of foreign investments, the foreign investor's share in the form of money is not less than 5 million US dollars, profit tax from legal entities, value added tax (realization of goods, works, services turnover), property tax, beautification and social infrastructure development tax, single social payment, single tax payment, as well as obligatory to the Republican road fund and the non-budget fund for the development of the material and technical base of educational and medical institutions under the Ministry of Finance of the Republic of Uzbekistan these enterprises have the right to apply the norms and rules of payment of deductions that were in effect on the date of state registration;

- within the framework of investment projects whose value exceeds 50 million US dollars and the share of a foreign investor is at least 50 percent, the construction of the necessary external engineering and communication networks outside the production area is carried out at the expense of budget funds and other internal financing sources;

- simplification of the visa procedure for employees of foreign companies participating in the implementation of investment projects (registration of entry and multiple-entry visas for a period of 12 months), systematic collection of necessary economic information, taking into account the budget and its implementation, monetary policy, foreign trade and other indicators opportunities for wide use in the manner specified in the basis. Uzbekistan

Republic of the President dated According to Decree No. 4434:

Uzbekistan of the President of the Republic in the year According to Decree No. F-3594: "Foreign Direct Investments"³The specific features of the application of special tax benefits in the following private foreign investment volumes are provided for enterprises specialized in the production of products (providing services) in the economic sectors listed in accordance with the annex, in accordance with the procedure established by the Tax Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Investors in New Uzbekistan expressed their satisfaction that all opportunities are being created for them to feel free, to look forward to the future with great confidence, and to work stably. The most important thing is that the Council of Foreign Investors has been established under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan and that investors' problems are solved openly in it, which arouses great interest among foreign investors.

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